

FOUR AND FIVE FIGURES OF LEKAN (POWER OF BASE 5) AND ANTILEKAN (ANTIPOWER OF BASE 5) TABLES AS A TOOL FOR MATHEMATICAL COMPUTATION

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Abstract

This paper presents the four and five figures of Lekan (Power of base 5) and AntiLekan (Antipower of base 5) tables as a tool for mathematical computation.

Table 1: Lekan (Power of base 5) of Number in Four Figure

(x)											Differences								
	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.0000	0.0592	0.1133	0.1630	0.2091	0.2519	0.2920	0.3297	0.3652	0.3988	44	89	132	176	219	262	305	347	389
2	0.4307	0.4610	0.4899	0.5175	0.5440	0.5693	0.5937	0.6171	0.6397	0.6615	26	51	77	102	127	152	177	202	227
3	0.6826	0.7030	0.7227	0.7418	0.7604	0.7784	0.7959	0.8129	0.8295	0.8456	18	36	54	72	90	108	126	143	161
4	0.8614	0.8767	0.8917	0.9063	0.9206	0.9345	0.9482	0.9616	0.9746	0.9874	14	28	42	56	70	84	97	111	125
5	1.0000	1.0123	1.0244	1.0362	1.0478	1.0592	1.0704	1.0814	1.0922	1.1028	11	23	34	46	57	68	80	91	102
6	1.1133	1.1236	1.1337	1.1436	1.1534	1.1630	1.1725	1.1818	1.1911	1.2001	10	19	29	38	48	58	67	77	86
7	1.2091	1.2179	1.2266	1.2351	1.2436	1.2519	1.2602	1.2683	1.2763	1.2842	8	17	25	33	42	50	58	66	75
8	1.2920	1.2997	1.3074	1.3149	1.3223	1.3297	1.3370	1.3441	1.3512	1.3583	7	15	22	29	37	44	51	59	66
9	1.3652	1.3721	1.3789	1.3856	1.3922	1.3988	1.4053	1.4118	1.4181	1.4244	7	13	20	26	33	39	46	52	59
10	1.4307	1.4369	1.4430	1.4490	1.4550	1.4610	1.4669	1.4727	1.4785	1.4842	6	12	18	24	30	36	42	47	53
11	1.4899	1.4955	1.5011	1.5066	1.5121	1.5175	1.5229	1.5282	1.5335	1.5388	5	11	16	22	27	32	38	43	49
12	1.5440	1.5491	1.5542	1.5593	1.5643	1.5693	1.5743	1.5792	1.5841	1.5889	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45
13	1.5937	1.5985	1.6032	1.6079	1.6125	1.6171	1.6217	1.6263	1.6308	1.6353	5	9	14	18	23	28	32	37	41
14	1.6397	1.6442	1.6486	1.6529	1.6572	1.6615	1.6658	1.6701	1.6743	1.6785	4	9	13	17	21	26	30	34	39
15	1.6826	1.6867	1.6908	1.6949	1.6990	1.7030	1.7070	1.7109	1.7149	1.7188	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36
16	1.7227	1.7266	1.7304	1.7342	1.7380	1.7418	1.7456	1.7493	1.7530	1.7567	4	8	11	15	19	23	26	30	34
17	1.7604	1.7640	1.7676	1.7712	1.7748	1.7784	1.7819	1.7854	1.7889	1.7924	4	7	11	14	18	21	25	28	32
18	1.7959	1.7993	1.8028	1.8062	1.8095	1.8129	1.8163	1.8196	1.8229	1.8262	3	7	10	13	17	20	24	27	30
19	1.8295	1.8327	1.8360	1.8392	1.8424	1.8456	1.8488	1.8520	1.8551	1.8582	3	6	10	12	16	19	21	26	29
20	1.8614	1.8645	1.8675	1.8706	1.8737	1.8767	1.8797	1.8827	1.8857	1.8887	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27
21	1.8917	1.8946	1.8976	1.9005	1.9034	1.9063	1.9092	1.9120	1.9149	1.9177	3	6	9	12	14	17	20	23	26
22	1.9206	1.9234	1.9262	1.9290	1.9318	1.9345	1.9373	1.9400	1.9428	1.9455	3	6	8	11	14	17	19	22	25
23	1.9482	1.9509	1.9536	1.9562	1.9589	1.9616	1.9642	1.9668	1.9694	1.9720	3	5	8	11	13	16	19	21	24
24	1.9746	1.9772	1.9798	1.9824	1.9849	1.9874	1.9900	1.9925	1.9950	1.9975	3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23
25	2.0000	2.0025	2.0050	2.0074	2.0099	2.0123	2.0147	2.0172	2.0196	2.0220	2	5	7	10	12	15	17	20	22
26	2.0244	2.0268	2.0291	2.0315	2.0339	2.0362	2.0385	2.0409	2.0432	2.0455	2	5	7	9	12	14	16	19	21
27	2.0478	2.0501	2.0524	2.0547	2.0570	2.0592	2.0615	2.0637	2.0660	2.0682	2	5	7	9	11	14	16	18	20
28	2.0704	2.0726	2.0748	2.0770	2.0792	2.0814	2.0836	2.0858	2.0879	2.0901	2	4	7	9	11	13	15	17	20
29	2.0922	2.0944	2.0965	2.0986	2.1007	2.1028	2.1049	2.1070	2.1091	2.1112	2	4	6	8	11	13	15	17	19
30	2.1133	2.1154	2.1174	2.1195	2.1215	2.1236	2.1256	2.1276	2.1296	2.1316	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
31	2.1337	2.1357	2.1377	2.1396	2.1416	2.1436	2.1456	2.1475	2.1495	2.1514	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18
32	2.1534	2.1553	2.1573	2.1592	2.1611	2.1630	2.1649	2.1668	2.1687	2.1706	2	4	6	8	10	11	13	15	17
33	2.1725	2.1744	2.1763	2.1781	2.1800	2.1818	2.1837	2.1855	2.1874	2.1892	2	4	6	7	9	11	13	15	17
34	2.1911	2.1929	2.1947	2.1965	2.1983	2.2001	2.2019	2.2037	2.2055	2.2073	2	4	5	7	9	11	13	14	16
35	2.2091	2.2108	2.2126	2.2144	2.2161	2.2179	2.2196	2.2214	2.2231	2.2248	2	4	5	7	9	11	12	14	16
36	2.2266	2.2283	2.2300	2.2317	2.2334	2.2351	2.2368	2.2385	2.2402	2.2419	2	3	5	7	9	10	12	14	15
37	2.2436	2.2453	2.2469	2.2486	2.2503	2.2519	2.2536	2.2552	2.2569	2.2585	2	3	5	7	8	10	12	13	15
38	2.2602	2.2618	2.2634	2.2650	2.2667	2.2683	2.2699	2.2715	2.2731	2.2747	2	3	5	6	8	10	11	13	15
39	2.2763	2.2779	2.2795	2.2811	2.2826	2.2842	2.2858	2.2874	2.2889	2.2905	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	13	14
40	2.2920	2.2936	2.2951	2.2967	2.2982	2.2997	2.3013	2.3028	2.3043	2.3059	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	12	14
41	2.3074	2.3089	2.3104	2.3119	2.3134	2.3149	2.3164	2.3179	2.3194	2.3209	1	3	4	6	7	9	10	12	13
42	2.3223	2.3238	2.3253	2.3268	2.3282	2.3297	2.3312	2.3326	2.3341	2.3355	1	3	4	6	7	9	10	12	13
43	2.3370	2.3384	2.3398	2.3413	2.3427	2.3441	2.3456	2.3470	2.3484	2.3498	1	3	4	6	7	9	10	11	13
44	2.3512	2.3527	2.3541	2.3555	2.3569	2.3583	2.3597	2.3611	2.3624	2.3638	1	3	4	6	7	8	10	11	13
45	2.3652	2.3666	2.3680	2.3693	2.3707	2.3721	2.3734	2.3748	2.3762	2.3775	1	3	4	5	7	8	10	11	12
46	2.3789	2.3802	2.3816	2.3829	2.3842	2.3856	2.3869	2.3883	2.3896	2.3909	1	3	4	5	7	8	9	11	12
47	2.3922	2.3936	2.3949	2.3962	2.3975	2.3988	2.4001	2.4014	2.4027	2.4040	1	3	4	5	7	8	9	10	12
48	2.4053	2.4066	2.4079	2.4092	2.4105	2.4118	2.4130	2.4143	2.4156	2.4169	1	3	4	5	6	8	9	10	12
49	2.4181	2.4194	2.4207	2.4219	2.4232	2.4244	2.4257	2.4269	2.4282	2.4294	1	3	4	5	6	8	9	10	11
50	2.4307	2.4319	2.4332	2.4344	2.4356	2.4369	2.4381	2.4393	2.4405	2.4418	1	2	4	5	6	7	9	10	11
51	2.4430	2.4442	2.4454	2.4466	2.4478	2.4490	2.4502	2.4515	2.4527	2.4538	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	10	11
52	2.4550	2.4562	2.4574	2.4586	2.4598	2.4610	2.4622	2.4634	2.4646	2.4657	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	11
53	2.4669	2.4681	2.4692	2.4704	2.4716	2.4727	2.4739	2.4750	2.4762	2.4773	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	10
54	2.4785	2.4796	2.4808	2.4819	2.4831	2.4842	2.4854	2.4865	2.4876	2.4888	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	10
55	2.4899	2.4910	2.4922	2.4933	2.4944	2.4955	2.4966	2.4977	2.4989	2.5000	1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	10
56	2.5011	2.5022	2.5033	2.5044	2.5055	2.5066	2.5077	2.5088	2.5099	2.5110	1	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	10
57	2.5121	2.5132	2.5143	2.5154	2.5164	2.5175	2.5186	2.5197	2.5207	2.5218	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	9	10

58	2.5229	2.5240	2.5250	2.5261	2.5272	2.5282	2.5293	2.5303	2.5314	2.5325		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	10
59	2.5335	2.5346	2.5356	2.5367	2.5377	2.5388	2.5398	2.5408	2.5419	2.5429		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
60	2.5440	2.5450	2.5460	2.5471	2.5481	2.5491	2.5501	2.5512	2.5522	2.5532		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
61	2.5542	2.5552	2.5563	2.5573	2.5583	2.5593	2.5603	2.5613	2.5623	2.5633		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
62	2.5643	2.5653	2.5663	2.5673	2.5683	2.5693	2.5703	2.5713	2.5723	2.5733		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
63	2.5743	2.5753	2.5762	2.5772	2.5782	2.5792	2.5802	2.5811	2.5821	2.5831		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
64	2.5841	2.5850	2.5860	2.5870	2.5879	2.5889	2.5899	2.5908	2.5918	2.5927		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
65	2.5937	2.5946	2.5956	2.5966	2.5975	2.5985	2.5994	2.6003	2.6013	2.6022		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
66	2.6032	2.6041	2.6051	2.6060	2.6069	2.6079	2.6088	2.6097	2.6107	2.6116		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
67	2.6125	2.6134	2.6144	2.6153	2.6162	2.6171	2.6181	2.6190	2.6199	2.6208		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
68	2.6217	2.6226	2.6236	2.6245	2.6254	2.6263	2.6272	2.6281	2.6290	2.6299		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
69	2.6308	2.6317	2.6326	2.6335	2.6344	2.6353	2.6362	2.6371	2.6380	2.6389		1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7	8
70	2.6397	2.6406	2.6415	2.6424	2.6433	2.6442	2.6450	2.6459	2.6468	2.6477		1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7	8
71	2.6486	2.6494	2.6503	2.6512	2.6520	2.6529	2.6538	2.6546	2.6555	2.6564		1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
72	2.6572	2.6581	2.6590	2.6598	2.6607	2.6615	2.6624	2.6633	2.6641	2.6650		1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
73	2.6658	2.6667	2.6675	2.6684	2.6692	2.6701	2.6709	2.6717	2.6726	2.6734		1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
74	2.6743	2.6751	2.6759	2.6768	2.6776	2.6785	2.6793	2.6801	2.6809	2.6818		1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8
75	2.6826	2.6834	2.6843	2.6851	2.6859	2.6867	2.6876	2.6884	2.6892	2.6900		1	2	2	3	4	5	6	7	7
76	2.6908	2.6917	2.6925	2.6933	2.6941	2.6949	2.6957	2.6965	2.6973	2.6982		1	2	2	3	4	5	6	6	7
77	2.6990	2.6998	2.7006	2.7014	2.7022	2.7030	2.7038	2.7046	2.7054	2.7062		1	2	2	3	4	5	6	6	7
78	2.7070	2.7078	2.7086	2.7094	2.7102	2.7109	2.7117	2.7125	2.7133	2.7141		1	2	2	3	4	5	6	6	7
79	2.7149	2.7157	2.7165	2.7172	2.7180	2.7188	2.7196	2.7204	2.7212	2.7219		1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
80	2.7227	2.7235	2.7243	2.7250	2.7258	2.7266	2.7273	2.7281	2.7289	2.7297		1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
81	2.7304	2.7312	2.7320	2.7327	2.7335	2.7342	2.7350	2.7358	2.7365	2.7373		1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
82	2.7380	2.7388	2.7396	2.7403	2.7411	2.7418	2.7426	2.7433	2.7441	2.7448		1	2	2	3	4	5	5	6	7
83	2.7456	2.7463	2.7471	2.7478	2.7486	2.7493	2.7501	2.7508	2.7515	2.7523		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
84	2.7530	2.7538	2.7545	2.7552	2.7560	2.7567	2.7574	2.7582	2.7589	2.7596		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
85	2.7604	2.7611	2.7618	2.7626	2.7633	2.7640	2.7647	2.7655	2.7662	2.7669		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	7
86	2.7676	2.7684	2.7691	2.7698	2.7705	2.7712	2.7720	2.7727	2.7734	2.7741		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	6
87	2.7748	2.7755	2.7763	2.7770	2.7777	2.7784	2.7791	2.7798	2.7805	2.7812		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	6
88	2.7819	2.7826	2.7833	2.7840	2.7847	2.7854	2.7861	2.7868	2.7875	2.7882		1	1	2	3	4	4	5	6	6
89	2.7889	2.7896	2.7903	2.7910	2.7917	2.7924	2.7931	2.7938	2.7945	2.7952		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	6
90	2.7959	2.7966	2.7973	2.7980	2.7986	2.7993	2.8000	2.8007	2.8014	2.8021		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
91	2.8028	2.8034	2.8041	2.8048	2.8055	2.8062	2.8068	2.8075	2.8082	2.8089		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
92	2.8095	2.8102	2.8109	2.8116	2.8122	2.8129	2.8136	2.8143	2.8149	2.8156		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
93	2.8163	2.8169	2.8176	2.8183	2.8189	2.8196	2.8203	2.8209	2.8216	2.8222		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
94	2.8229	2.8236	2.8242	2.8249	2.8255	2.8262	2.8269	2.8275	2.8282	2.8288		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
95	2.8295	2.8301	2.8308	2.8314	2.8321	2.8327	2.8334	2.8340	2.8347	2.8353		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
96	2.8360	2.8366	2.8373	2.8379	2.8386	2.8392	2.8399	2.8405	2.8411	2.8418		1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	6
97	2.8424	2.8431	2.8437	2.8443	2.8450	2.8456	2.8463	2.8469	2.8475	2.8482		1	1	2	3	3	4	4	5	6
98	2.8488	2.8494	2.8501	2.8507	2.8513	2.8520	2.8526	2.8532	2.8539	2.8545		1	1	2	3	3	4	4	5	6
99	2.8551	2.8557	2.8564	2.8570	2.8576	2.8582	2.8589	2.8595	2.8601	2.8607		1	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6

Table 2: Lekan (Power of base 5) of 10^n in Four Figures

$Lek(10^n)$

10^n	5^1	10^n	5^2	10^n	5^3	10^n	5^4	10^n	5^5	10^n	5^6	10^n	5^7
	$Lek(10^n)$												
1	1.4307	16	22.8908	31	44.3510	46	65.8111	61	87.2713	76	108.7314	91	130.1916
2	2.8614	17	24.3215	32	45.7816	47	67.2418	62	88.7019	77	110.1621	92	131.6222
3	4.2920	18	25.7522	33	47.2123	48	68.6725	63	90.1326	78	111.5928	93	133.0529
4	5.7227	19	27.1829	34	48.6430	49	70.1032	64	91.5633	79	113.0234	94	134.4836
5	7.1534	20	28.6135	35	50.0737	50	71.5338	65	92.9940	80	114.4541	95	135.9143
6	8.5841	21	30.0442	36	51.5044	51	72.9645	66	94.4247	81	115.8848	96	137.3449
7	10.0147	22	31.4749	37	52.9350	52	74.3952	67	95.8553	82	117.3155	97	138.7756
8	11.4454	23	32.9056	38	54.3657	53	75.8259	68	97.2860	83	118.7462	98	140.2063
9	12.8761	24	34.3362	39	55.7964	54	77.2565	69	98.7167	84	120.1768	99	141.6370
10	14.3068	25	35.7669	40	57.2271	55	78.6872	70	100.1474	85	121.6075		
11	15.7374	26	37.1976	41	58.6577	56	80.1179	71	101.5780	86	123.0382		
12	17.1681	27	38.6283	42	60.0884	57	81.5486	72	103.0087	87	124.4689		
13	18.5988	28	40.0589	43	61.5191	58	82.9792	73	104.4394	88	125.8995		
14	20.0295	29	41.4896	44	62.9498	59	84.4099	74	105.8701	89	127.3302		
15	21.4601	30	42.9203	45	64.3804	60	85.8406	75	107.3007	90	128.7609		

Table 3: AntiLek (AntiPower of base 5) of Number in Four Figures

$x \rightarrow$ AntiLek x

(x)	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.009		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
												Differences								
0	1.0000	1.0016	1.0032	1.0048	1.0065	1.0081	1.0097	1.0113	1.013	1.0146		2	3	5	6	8	10	11	13	15
0.01	1.0162	1.0179	1.0032	1.0048	1.0065	1.0081	1.0097	1.0113	1.0130	1.0146		2	3	5	7	8	10	12	13	15
0.02	1.0327	1.0344	1.0195	1.0211	1.0228	1.0244	1.0261	1.0277	1.0294	1.0311		2	3	5	7	8	10	12	13	15
0.03	1.0495	1.0512	1.0360	1.0377	1.0394	1.0411	1.0427	1.0444	1.0461	1.0478		2	3	5	7	9	10	12	14	15
0.04	1.0665	1.0682	1.0529	1.0545	1.0562	1.0579	1.0597	1.0614	1.0631	1.0648		2	3	5	7	9	10	12	14	16
0.05	1.0838	1.0855	1.0699	1.0717	1.0734	1.0751	1.0768	1.0786	1.0803	1.0821		2	4	5	7	9	11	12	14	16
0.06	1.1014	1.1032	1.0873	1.0890	1.0908	1.0926	1.0943	1.0961	1.0978	1.0996		2	4	5	7	9	11	13	14	16
0.07	1.1193	1.1211	1.1049	1.1067	1.1085	1.1103	1.1121	1.1139	1.1157	1.1175		2	4	5	7	9	11	13	15	16
0.08	1.1374	1.1392	1.1229	1.1247	1.1265	1.1283	1.1301	1.1319	1.1338	1.1356		2	4	6	7	9	11	13	15	17
0.09	1.1559	1.1577	1.1411	1.1429	1.1448	1.1466	1.1484	1.1503	1.1522	1.1540		2	4	6	7	9	11	13		

0.17	1.3147	1.3168	1.2979	1.3000	1.3021	1.3042	1.3063	1.3084	1.3105	1.3126		2	4	6	9	11	13	15	17	19
0.18	1.336	1.3382	1.3189	1.3211	1.3232	1.3253	1.3275	1.3296	1.3317	1.3339		2	4	6	9	11	13	15	17	20
0.19	1.3577	1.3599	1.3403	1.3425	1.3447	1.3468	1.3490	1.3512	1.3533	1.3555		2	4	7	9	11	13	15	18	20
0.20	1.3797	1.3820	1.3621	1.3643	1.3665	1.3687	1.3709	1.3731	1.3753	1.3775		2	4	7	9	11	13	16	18	20
0.21	1.4021	1.4044	1.3842	1.3864	1.3886	1.3909	1.3931	1.3954	1.3976	1.3999		2	5	7	9	11	14	16	18	20
0.22	1.4249	1.4272	1.4066	1.4089	1.4112	1.4134	1.4157	1.4180	1.4203	1.4226		2	5	7	9	12	14	16	18	21
0.23	1.4480	1.4503	1.4295	1.4318	1.4341	1.4364	1.4387	1.4410	1.4433	1.4457		2	5	7	9	12	14	16	19	21
0.24	1.4715	1.4738	1.4527	1.4550	1.4573	1.4597	1.4620	1.4644	1.4667	1.4691		2	5	7	10	12	14	17	19	21
0.25	1.4953	1.4978	1.4762	1.4786	1.4810	1.4834	1.4858	1.4881	1.4905	1.4929		2	5	7	10	12	15	17	19	22
0.26	1.5196	1.5221	1.5002	1.5026	1.505	1.5074	1.5099	1.5123	1.5147	1.5172		2	5	7	10	12	15	17	20	22
0.27	1.5443	1.5468	1.5245	1.5270	1.5294	1.5319	1.5344	1.5368	1.5393	1.5418		3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23
0.28	1.5693	1.5718	1.5492	1.5517	1.5542	1.5567	1.5592	1.5618	1.5643	1.5668		3	5	8	10	13	15	18	20	23
0.29	1.5948	1.5974	1.5744	1.5769	1.5795	1.5820	1.5845	1.5871	1.5897	1.5922		3	5	8	10	13	16	18	21	23
0.30	1.6207	1.6233	1.5999	1.6025	1.6051	1.6077	1.6103	1.6129	1.6154	1.6181		3	5	8	11	13	16	18	21	24
0.31	1.6470	1.6496	1.6259	1.6285	1.6311	1.6338	1.6364	1.6390	1.6417	1.6443		3	5	8	11	13	16	19	21	24
0.32	1.6737	1.6764	1.6523	1.6549	1.6576	1.6603	1.6629	1.6656	1.6683	1.6710		3	5	8	11	14	16	19	22	24
0.33	1.7008	1.7036	1.6791	1.6818	1.6845	1.6872	1.6899	1.6926	1.6954	1.6981		3	6	8	11	14	17	19	22	25
0.34	1.7284	1.7312	1.7063	1.7091	1.7118	1.7146	1.7173	1.7201	1.7229	1.7256		3	6	8	11	14	17	20	22	25
0.35	1.7565	1.7593	1.7340	1.7368	1.7396	1.7424	1.7452	1.7480	1.7508	1.7536		3	6	9	11	14	17	20	23	26
0.36	1.7850	1.7878	1.7621	1.7650	1.7678	1.7707	1.7735	1.7764	1.7792	1.7821		3	6	9	12	14	17	20	23	26
0.37	1.8139	1.8168	1.7907	1.7936	1.7965	1.7994	1.8023	1.8052	1.8081	1.8111		3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	26
0.38	1.8434	1.8463	1.8198	1.8227	1.8256	1.8286	1.8315	1.8345	1.8374	1.8404		3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27
0.39	1.8733	1.8763	1.8493	1.8523	1.8553	1.8582	1.8612	1.8642	1.8672	1.8702		3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27
0.40	1.9037	1.9067	1.8793	1.8823	1.8854	1.8884	1.8914	1.8945	1.8975	1.9006		3	6	9	12	15	19	22	25	28
0.41	1.9345	1.9377	1.9098	1.9129	1.9159	1.9190	1.9221	1.9252	1.9283	1.9314		3	6	9	13	16	19	22	25	28
0.42	1.9659	1.9691	1.9408	1.9439	1.9470	1.9502	1.9533	1.9565	1.9596	1.9628		3	6	10	13	16	19	22	26	29
0.43	1.9978	2.0010	1.9723	1.9754	1.9786	1.9818	1.9850	1.9882	1.9914	1.9946		3	6	10	13	16	19	23	26	29
0.44	2.0302	2.0335	2.0043	2.0075	2.0107	2.0140	2.0172	2.0205	2.0237	2.0270		3	7	10	13	16	20	23	26	30
0.45	2.0632	2.0665	2.0368	2.0401	2.0433	2.0466	2.0499	2.0532	2.0565	2.0599		3	7	10	13	17	20	23	27	30
0.46	2.0967	2.1000	2.0698	2.0732	2.0765	2.0798	2.0832	2.0866	2.0899	2.0933		3	7	10	14	17	20	24	27	31
0.47	2.1307	2.1341	2.1034	2.1068	2.1102	2.1136	2.1170	2.1204	2.1238	2.1272		3	7	10	14	17	21	24	28	31
0.48	2.1652	2.1687	2.1375	2.1410	2.1444	2.1479	2.1513	2.1548	2.1583	2.1618		4	7	11	14	18	21	25	28	32
0.49	2.2004	2.2039	2.1722	2.1757	2.1792	2.1827	2.1862	2.1898	2.1933	2.1968		4	7	11	14	18	21	25	29	32
0.50	2.2361	2.2397	2.2075	2.2110	2.2146	2.2181	2.2217	2.2253	2.2289	2.2325		4	7	11	15	18	22	25	29	33
0.51	2.2723	2.2760	2.2433	2.2469	2.2505	2.2541	2.2578	2.2614	2.2650	2.2687		4	7	11	15	18	22	26	29	33
0.52	2.3092	2.3129	2.2797	2.2833	2.2870	2.2907	2.2944	2.2981	2.3018	2.3055		4	7	11	15	19	22	26	30	34
0.53	2.3467	2.3505	2.3167	2.3204	2.3241	2.3279	2.3316	2.3354	2.3391	2.3429		4	8	11	15	19	23	27	30	34
0.54	2.3848	2.3886	2.3542	2.3580	2.3618	2.3656	2.3695	2.3733	2.3771	2.3809		4	8	12	15	19	23	27	31	35
0.55	2.4234	2.4274	2.3924	2.3963	2.4002	2.4040	2.4079	2.4118	2.4157	2.4195		4	8	12	16	20	24	28	31	35
0.56	2.4628	2.4667	2.4313	2.4352	2.4391	2.4430	2.4470	2.4509	2.4549	2.4588		4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36
0.57	2.5027	2.5068	2.4707	2.4747	2.4787	2.4827	2.4867	2.4907	2.4947	2.4987		4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	37
0.58	2.5433	2.5474	2.5108	2.5148	2.5189	2.5229	2.5270	2.5311	2.5352	2.5392		4	8	12	16	21	25	29	33	37
0.59	2.5846	2.5888	2.5515	2.5556	2.5598	2.5639	2.5680	2.5721	2.5763	2.5804		4	8	13	17	21	25	29	34	38
0.60	2.6265	2.6308	2.5929	2.5971	2.6013	2.6055	2.6097	2.6139	2.6181	2.6223		4	9	13	17	21	26	30	34	38
0.61	2.6691	2.6734	2.6350	2.6392	2.6435	2.6477	2.6520	2.6563	2.6606	2.6648		4	9	13	17	22	26	30	35	39
0.62	2.7124	2.7168	2.6777	2.6821	2.6864	2.6907	2.6950	2.6994	2.7037	2.7081		4	9	13	18	22	26	31	35	40
0.63	2.7565	2.7609	2.7212	2.7256	2.7300	2.7344	2.7388	2.7432	2.7476	2.7520		4	9	13	18	22	27	31	36	40
0.64	2.8012	2.8057	2.7653	2.7698	2.7743	2.7787	2.7832	2.7877	2.7922	2.7967		5	9	14	18	23	27	32	36	41
0.65	2.8466	2.8512	2.8102	2.8147	2.8193	2.8238	2.8284	2.8329	2.8375	2.8420		5	9	14	18	23	28	32	37	42
0.66	2.8928	2.8975	2.8558	2.8604	2.8650	2.8696	2.8742	2.8789	2.8835	2.8882		5	9	14	19	23	28	33	38	42
0.67	2.9397	2.9445	2.9021	2.9068	2.9115	2.9162	2.9209	2.9256	2.9303	2.9350		5	10	14	19	24	29	33	38	43
0.68	2.9874	2.9923	2.9492	2.9540	2.9587	2.9635	2.9683	2.9731	2.9778	2.9825		5	10	15	19	24	29	34	39	44
0.69	3.0359	3.0408	2.9971	3.0019	3.0067	3.0116	3.0164	3.0213	3.0262	3.0310		5	10	15	20	25	30	34	39	44
0.70	3.0852	3.0901	3.0457	3.0506	3.0555	3.0604	3.0654	3.0703	3.0753	3.0802		5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45
0.71	3.1352	3.1403	3.0951	3.1001	3.1051	3.1101	3.1151	3.1201	3.1251	3.1302		5	10	15	20	25	31	36	41	46
0.72	3.1861	3.1912	3.1453	3.1504	3.1555	3.1606	3.1656	3.1707	3.1759	3.1810		5	10	15	21	26	31	36	41	47
0.73	3.2378	3.2430	3.1964	3.2015	3.2067	3.2118	3.2170	3.2222	3.2274	3.2326		5	10	16	21	26	32	37	42	47
0.74	3.2903	3.2956	3.2482	3.2535	3.2587	3.2639	3.2692	3.2745	3.2797	3.2850		5	11	16	21	27	32	37	43	48
0.75	3.3437	3.3491	3.3009	3.3062	3.3116	3.3169	3.3222	3.3276	3.3330	3.3383		5	11	16	22	27	33	38	43	49
0.76	3.3980	3.4034	3.3545	3.3599	3.3653	3.3707	3.3761	3.3816	3.3870	3.3925		6	11	17	22	28	33	39	44	50
0.77	3.4531	3.4586	3.4089	3.4144	3.4199	3.4254	3.4309	3.4364	3.4420	3.4475		6	11	17	22	28	34	39	45	50
0.78	3.5091	3.5148	3.4642	3.4698	3.4754	3.4810	3.4866	3.4922	3.4978	3.5035		6	11	17	23	28	34	40	46	51
0.79	3.5660	3.5718	3.5204	3.5261	3.5318	3.5375	3.5432	3.5489	3.5546	3.5603		6	12	17	23	29	35	40	46	52
0.80	3.6239	3.6297	3.5775	3.5833	3.5891	3.5949	3.6006	3.6064	3.6123	3.6181		6	12	18	24	29	35	41	47	53
0.81	3.6827	3.6886	3.6356	3.6414	3.6473	3.6532	3.6591	3.6650	3.6709	3.6768		6	12	18	24	30	36	42	48	54
0.82	3.7424	3.7485	3.6946	3.7005	3.7065	3.7124														

Table 4: Conversion of 5^y to 10^n in Four Figures

$5^y \rightarrow 10^n$

5^y	10^n												
1	0.6990	16	11.1835	31	21.6681	46	32.1526	61	42.6372	76	53.1217	91	63.6063
2	1.3979	17	11.8825	32	22.3670	47	32.8516	62	43.3361	77	53.8207	92	64.3052
3	2.0969	18	12.5815	33	23.0660	48	33.5506	63	44.0351	78	54.5197	93	65.0042
4	2.7959	19	13.2804	34	23.7650	49	34.2495	64	44.7341	79	55.2186	94	65.7032
5	3.4949	20	13.9794	35	24.4640	50	34.9485	65	45.4331	80	55.9176	95	66.4022
6	4.1938	21	14.6784	36	25.1629	51	35.6475	66	46.1320	81	56.6166	96	67.1011
7	4.8928	22	15.3773	37	25.8619	52	36.3464	67	46.8310	82	57.3155	97	67.8001
8	5.5918	23	16.0763	38	26.5609	53	37.0454	68	47.5300	83	58.0145	98	68.4991
9	6.2907	24	16.7753	39	27.2598	54	37.7444	69	48.2289	84	58.7135	99	69.198
10	6.9897	25	17.4743	40	27.9588	55	38.4434	70	48.9279	85	59.4125		
11	7.6887	26	18.1732	41	28.6578	56	39.1423	71	49.6269	86	60.1114		
12	8.3876	27	18.8722	42	29.3567	57	39.8413	72	50.3258	87	60.8104		
13	9.0866	28	19.5712	43	30.0557	58	40.5403	73	51.0248	88	61.5094		
14	9.7856	29	20.2701	44	30.7547	59	41.2392	74	51.7238	89	62.2083		
15	10.4846	30	20.9691	45	31.4537	60	41.9382	75	52.4228	90	62.9073		

Table 5: Lekan (Power of base 5) of Number in Five Figure

$x \rightarrow Lek\ x$

x											Differences								
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.0000	0.0592	0.1132	0.1630	0.2090	0.2519	0.2920	0.3297	0.3652	0.3988	44	88	132	176	219	262	304	350	389
2	0.4306	0.4609	0.4899	0.5175	0.5439	0.5693	0.5936	0.6171	0.6397	0.6615	25	51	76	102	122	152	177	204	227
3	0.6826	0.7029	0.7227	0.7418	0.7603	0.7783	0.7958	0.8129	0.8294	0.8456	18	36	54	72	90	107	125	145	161
4	0.8613	0.8767	0.8916	0.9062	0.9205	0.9345	0.9481	0.9615	0.9746	0.9874	14	28	41	55	69	83	97	112	124
5	1.0000	1.0123	1.0243	1.0362	1.0478	1.0592	1.0704	1.0814	1.0922	1.1028	11	22	34	45	56	68	79	91	102
6	1.1132	1.1235	1.1336	1.1436	1.1533	1.1630	1.1725	1.1818	1.1910	1.2001	9	19	28	38	48	57	67	77	86
7	1.2090	1.2178	1.2265	1.2351	1.2435	1.2519	1.2601	1.2682	1.2763	1.2842	8	16	25	33	41	49	58	67	74
8	1.2920	1.2997	1.3073	1.3149	1.3223	1.3297	1.3369	1.3441	1.3512	1.3582	7	14	22	29	36	44	51	59	65
9	1.3652	1.3720	1.3788	1.3855	1.3922	1.3988	1.4053	1.4117	1.4181	1.4244	6	13	19	26	32	39	45	53	58
10	1.4306	1.4368	1.4429	1.4490	1.4550	1.4609	1.4668	1.4727	1.4785	1.4842	5	11	17	23	29	35	41	48	53
11	1.4899	1.4955	1.5010	1.5066	1.5120	1.5175	1.5229	1.5282	1.5335	1.5387	4	10	16	21	27	32	37	43	48
12	1.5439	1.5491	1.5542	1.5593	1.5643	1.5693	1.5742	1.5791	1.5840	1.5888	3	9	15	19	24	29	34	40	44
13	1.5936	1.5984	1.6031	1.6078	1.6125	1.6171	1.6217	1.6262	1.6308	1.6352	2	8	13	18	23	27	32	37	41
14	1.6397	1.6441	1.6485	1.6529	1.6572	1.6615	1.6658	1.6700	1.6742	1.6784	1	7	12	17	21	25	30	34	38
15	1.6826	1.6867	1.6908	1.6949	1.6989	1.7029	1.7069	1.7109	1.7148	1.7188		6	11	16	20	24	28	32	36
16	1.7227	1.7265	1.7304	1.7342	1.7380	1.7418	1.7455	1.7493	1.7530	1.7567		5	10	15	19	23	27	31	35
17	1.7603	1.7640	1.7676	1.7712	1.7748	1.7783	1.7819	1.7854	1.7889	1.7924		4	9	14	18	22	26	30	34
18	1.7958	1.7993	1.8027	1.8061	1.8095	1.8129	1.8162	1.8195	1.8229	1.8262		3	8	13	17	21	25	29	33
19	1.8294	1.8327	1.8359	1.8392	1.8424	1.8456	1.8488	1.8519	1.8551	1.8582		2	7	12	16	19	23	27	31
20	1.8613	1.8644	1.8675	1.8706	1.8736	1.8767	1.8797	1.8827	1.8857	1.8887		1	6	11	15	18	22	26	30
21	1.8916	1.8946	1.8975	1.9004	1.9033	1.9062	1.9091	1.9120	1.9149	1.9177			5	10	14	17	20	24	28
22	1.9205	1.9233	1.9262	1.9291	1.9319	1.9347	1.9375	1.9403	1.9431	1.9458			4	9	13	16	19	23	27
23	1.9481	1.9508	1.9535	1.9562	1.9589	1.9615	1.9641	1.9668	1.9694	1.9720			3	8	12	15	18	22	26
24	1.9746	1.9772	1.9797	1.9823	1.9849	1.9874	1.9899	1.9925	1.9950	1.9975			2	7	11	14	17	21	25
25	2.0000	2.0024	2.0049	2.0074	2.0098	2.0123	2.0147	2.0171	2.0195	2.0219			1	6	10	14	17	21	25
26	2.0243	2.0267	2.0291	2.0315	2.0338	2.0362	2.0385	2.0408	2.0432	2.0455				5	9	13	17	21	25
27	2.0478	2.0501	2.0524	2.0546	2.0569	2.0592	2.0614	2.0637	2.0659	2.0681				4	8	12	16	20	24
28	2.0704	2.0726	2.0748	2.0770	2.0792	2.0814	2.0835	2.0857	2.0879	2.0900				3	7	11	15	19	23
29	2.0922	2.0943	2.0964	2.0985	2.1007	2.1028	2.1049	2.1070	2.1091	2.1112				2	6	10	14	18	22
30	2.1132	2.1153	2.1174	2.1194	2.1215	2.1235	2.1255	2.1276	2.1296	2.1316				1	5	9	13	17	21
31	2.1336	2.1356	2.1376	2.1396	2.1416	2.1436	2.1455	2.1475	2.1494	2.1514					4	8	12	16	20
32	2.1533	2.1553	2.1572	2.1591	2.1611	2.1630	2.1649	2.1668	2.1687	2.1706					3	7	11	15	19
33	2.1725	2.1743	2.1762	2.1781	2.1799	2.1818	2.1837	2.1855	2.1873	2.1892					2	6	10	14	18
34	2.1910	2.1928	2.1947	2.1965	2.1983	2.2001	2.2019	2.2037	2.2055	2.2072					1	5	9	13	17
35	2.2090	2.2108	2.2126	2.2143	2.2161	2.2178	2.2196	2.2213	2.2231	2.2248						4	8	12	16
36	2.2265	2.2282	2.2300	2.2317	2.2334	2.2351	2.2368	2.2385	2.2402	2.2419						3	7	11	15
37	2.2435	2.2452	2.2469	2.2486	2.2502	2.2519	2.2535	2.2552	2.2568	2.2585						2	6	10	14
38	2.2601	2.2617	2.2634	2.2650	2.2666	2.2682	2.2698	2.2715	2.2731	2.2747						1	5	9	13

92	2.8095 5	2.8102 9	2.8108 7	2.8115 4	2.8122 2	2.8129 1	2.8135 8	2.8142 5	2.8149 2	2.8155 9		7	13	20	27	34	40	47	54	60
93	2.8162 6	2.8169 3	2.8176 0	2.8182 6	2.8189 3	2.8195 0	2.8202 7	2.8209 4	2.8215 1	2.8222 8		7	13	20	27	33	40	47	54	60
94	2.8229 1	2.8235 8	2.8242 5	2.8248 2	2.8255 9	2.8262 6	2.8268 3	2.8275 0	2.8281 7	2.8288 4		7	13	20	26	33	39	46	53	59
95	2.8294 4	2.8301 1	2.8307 8	2.8314 5	2.8320 2	2.8327 9	2.8333 6	2.8340 3	2.8346 0	2.8353 7		7	13	20	26	33	39	46	53	59
96	2.8359 9	2.8366 6	2.8372 3	2.8379 0	2.8385 7	2.8392 4	2.8398 1	2.8405 8	2.8411 5	2.8417 2		6	13	19	26	32	39	45	52	58
97	2.8424 3	2.8430 0	2.8437 7	2.8443 4	2.8449 1	2.8456 8	2.8462 5	2.8469 2	2.8475 9	2.8481 6		6	13	19	25	32	38	45	52	57
98	2.8488 8	2.8494 5	2.8500 2	2.8507 9	2.8513 6	2.8519 3	2.8525 0	2.8532 7	2.8538 4	2.8544 1		6	13	19	25	32	38	44	51	57
99	2.8551 1	2.8557 8	2.8563 5	2.8569 2	2.8576 9	2.8582 6	2.8588 3	2.8594 0	2.8601 7	2.8607 4		6	12	19	25	31	37	44	51	56

Table 6: Lekan (Power of base 5) of 10^n in Five Figures

$Lek(10^n)$

10^n	5^y										
10^n	$Lek(10^n)$										
n=1	y=1.43068	n=21	y=30.04421	n=41	y=58.65774	n=61	y=87.27127	n=81	y=115.88480		
2	2.86135	22	31.47488	42	60.08842	62	88.70195	82	117.31548		
3	4.29202	23	32.90556	43	61.51909	63	90.13262	83	118.74615		
4	5.72271	24	34.33624	44	62.94977	64	91.56330	84	120.17683		
5	7.15338	25	35.76691	45	64.38045	65	92.99398	85	121.60751		
6	8.58406	26	37.19759	46	65.81112	66	94.42465	86	123.03818		
7	10.01474	27	38.62827	47	67.24180	67	95.85533	87	124.46886		
8	11.44541	28	40.05894	48	68.67248	68	97.28601	88	125.89954		
9	12.87609	29	41.48962	49	70.10315	69	98.71668	89	127.33021		
10	14.30677	30	42.92030	50	71.53383	70	100.14736	90	128.76089		
11	15.73744	31	44.35097	51	72.96450	71	101.57804	91	130.19157		
12	17.16812	32	45.78165	52	74.39518	72	103.00871	92	131.62224		
13	18.59880	33	47.21233	53	75.82586	73	104.43939	93	133.05292		
14	20.02947	34	48.64300	54	77.25653	74	105.87007	94	134.48360		
15	21.46015	35	50.07368	55	78.68721	75	107.30074	95	135.91427		
16	22.89083	36	51.50436	56	80.11789	76	108.73142	96	137.34495		
17	24.32150	37	52.93503	57	81.54856	77	110.16209	97	138.77563		
18	25.75218	38	54.36571	58	82.97924	78	111.59277	98	140.20630		
19	27.18286	39	55.79639	59	84.40992	79	113.02345	99	141.63698		
20	28.61353	40	57.22706	60	85.84059	80	114.45412				

Table 7: AntiLekan (AntiPower of base 5) of Number in Five Figures

$x \rightarrow \text{AntiLek } x$

(x)											Differences									
	0	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.009	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
0.00	1.0000	1.0016	1.0032	1.0048	1.0064	1.0080	1.0097	1.0113	1.0129	1.0145	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
0.01	1.0162	1.0178	1.0195	1.0211	1.0227	1.0244	1.0260	1.0277	1.0293	1.0310	6	32	49	65	81	97	11	13	14	6
0.02	1.0327	1.0343	1.0360	1.0377	1.0393	1.0410	1.0427	1.0444	1.0461	1.0477	1	33	49	66	82	99	11	13	15	8
0.03	1.0494	1.0511	1.0528	1.0545	1.0562	1.0579	1.0596	1.0613	1.0630	1.0647	7	34	51	68	85	10	11	13	15	1
0.04	1.0665	1.0682	1.0699	1.0716	1.0733	1.0751	1.0768	1.0785	1.0803	1.0820	1	35	52	69	86	10	12	13	15	3
0.05	1.0838	1.0855	1.0872	1.0890	1.0908	1.0925	1.0943	1.0960	1.0978	1.0996	8	35	53	70	88	5	3	1	8	6
0.06	1.1013	1.1031	1.1049	1.1067	1.1085	1.1102	1.1120	1.1138	1.1156	1.1174	1	36	54	71	89	10	12	14	16	1
0.07	1.1192	1.1210	1.1228	1.1246	1.1264	1.1283	1.1301	1.1319	1.1337	1.1355	8	36	54	73	91	9	7	5	3	1
0.08	1.1374	1.1392	1.1410	1.1429	1.1447	1.1466	1.1484	1.1503	1.1521	1.1540	1	37	55	74	92	11	12	14	16	1
0.09	1.1558	1.1577	1.1595	1.1614	1.1633	1.1652	1.1670	1.1689	1.1708	1.1727	1	37	55	74	92	11	13	15	16	6
0.10	1.1746	1.1765	1.1784	1.1803	1.1822	1.1841	1.1860	1.1879	1.1898	1.1917	9	37	56	75	94	2	1	0	9	9
0.11	1.1936	1.1956	1.1975	1.1994	1.2013	1.2033	1.2052	1.2072	1.2091	1.2110	1	38	57	76	95	4	3	2	2	7
0.12	1.2130	1.2150	1.2169	1.2189	1.2208	1.2228	1.2248	1.2267	1.2287	1.2307	2	39	58	77	97	6	6	5	4	1
0.13	1.2327	1.2347	1.2367	1.2386	1.2406	1.2426	1.2446	1.2466	1.2487	1.2507	0	40	60	80	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.14	1.2527	1.2547	1.2567	1.2587	1.2608	1.2628	1.2648	1.2669	1.2689	1.2710	2	41	61	81	10	12	14	16	18	1
0.15	1.2730	1.2751	1.2771	1.2792	1.2812	1.2833	1.2854	1.2874	1.2895	1.2916	0	41	62	83	3	4	5	5	6	6
0.16	1.2937	1.2957	1.2978	1.2999	1.3020	1.3041	1.3062	1.3083	1.3104	1.3125	2	42	63	84	10	12	14	16	18	9
0.17	1.3147	1.3168	1.3189	1.3210	1.3231	1.3253	1.3274	1.3295	1.3317	1.3338	2	43	64	85	10	12	14	17	19	2
0.18	1.3360	1.3381	1.3403	1.3424	1.3446	1.3468	1.3489	1.3511	1.3533	1.3555	2	43	65	87	10	13	15	17	19	9
0.19	1.3577	1.3598	1.3620	1.3642	1.3664	1.3686	1.3708	1.3730	1.3753	1.3775	2	44	66	88	11	13	15	17	19	8
0.20	1.3797	1.3819	1.3841	1.3864	1.3886	1.3908	1.3931	1.3953	1.3976	1.3998	2	45	67	89	11	13	15	17	20	1
0.21	1.4021	1.4043	1.4066	1.4089	1.4111	1.4134	1.4157	1.4180	1.4202	1.4225	2	45	68	91	4	6	9	18	20	5
0.22	1.4248	1.4271	1.4294	1.4317	1.4340	1.4363	1.4386	1.4410	1.4433	1.4456	2	46	69	92	11	13	16	18	20	8
0.23	1.4479	1.4503	1.4526	1.4549	1.4573	1.4596	1.4620	1.4643	1.4667	1.4691	2	47	70	94	7	1	4	16	18	21
0.24	1.4714	1.4738	1.4762	1.4786	1.4809	1.4833	1.4857	1.4881	1.4905	1.4929	2	48	72	95	9	3	7	19	21	9
0.25	1.4953	1.4977	1.5001	1.5025	1.5050	1.5074	1.5098	1.5122	1.5147	1.5171	2	48	73	97	1	6	0	4	8	8
0.26	1.5196	1.5220	1.5245	1.5269	1.5294	1.5318	1.5343	1.5368	1.5393	1.5417	2	49	74	99	12	14	17	19	22	2

0.27	1.5442 7	1.5467 5	1.5492 4	1.5517 4	1.5542 4	1.5567 4	1.5592 5	1.5617 6	1.5642 8	1.5668 0	2	50	75	10	12	15	17	20	22	5
0.28	1.5693 2	1.5718 5	1.5743 2	1.5769 2	1.5794 6	1.5820 0	1.5845 5	1.5871 0	1.5896 2	1.5922 2	2	51	76	10	12	15	17	20	22	9
0.29	1.5947 8	1.5973 5	1.5999 0	1.6025 0	1.6050 8	1.6076 7	1.6102 6	1.6128 5	1.6154 5	1.6180 5	2	52	78	10	12	15	18	20	23	3
0.30	1.6206 6	1.6232 7	1.6258 8	1.6285 0	1.6311 2	1.6337 5	1.6363 8	1.6390 2	1.6416 6	1.6443 0	2	53	79	10	13	15	18	21	23	7
0.31	1.6469 5	1.6496 0	1.6522 6	1.6549 2	1.6575 9	1.6602 6	1.6629 3	1.6656 1	1.6682 9	1.6709 8	2	53	80	10	13	16	18	21	24	0
0.32	1.6736 7	1.6763 7	1.6790 7	1.6817 7	1.6844 8	1.6871 9	1.6899 1	1.6926 3	1.6953 6	1.6980 9	2	54	81	10	13	16	19	21	24	4
0.33	1.7008 3	1.7035 7	1.7063 1	1.7090 6	1.7118 1	1.7145 7	1.7173 3	1.7201 0	1.7228 7	1.7256 4	2	55	83	11	13	16	19	22	24	8
0.34	1.7284 2	1.7312 9	1.7339 9	1.7367 9	1.7395 9	1.7423 9	1.7451 9	1.7480 0	1.7508 2	1.7536 4	2	56	84	11	14	16	19	22	25	2
0.35	1.7564 3	1.7592 9	1.7621 3	1.7649 7	1.7678 1	1.7706 6	1.7735 7	1.7763 3	1.7792 9	1.7820 9	2	57	85	11	14	17	19	22	25	6
0.36	1.7849 6	1.7878 4	1.7907 2	1.7936 0	1.7964 9	1.7993 8	1.8022 8	1.8051 9	1.8080 1	1.8110 1	2	58	87	11	14	17	20	23	26	1
0.37	1.8139 2	1.8168 4	1.8197 7	1.8227 0	1.8256 4	1.8285 8	1.8315 2	1.8344 7	1.8374 3	1.8403 9	2	49	88	11	14	17	20	23	26	5
0.38	1.8433 5	1.8463 2	1.8493 0	1.8522 8	1.8552 6	1.8582 5	1.8612 4	1.8642 4	1.8672 5	1.8702 5	3	60	90	12	14	17	20	23	26	9
0.39	1.8732 6	1.8762 8	1.8793 3	1.8823 3	1.8853 6	1.8884 0	1.8914 4	1.8944 8	1.8975 4	1.9005 9	3	61	91	12	15	18	21	24	27	4
0.40	1.9036 5	1.9067 2	1.9097 9	1.9128 7	1.9159 5	1.9190 3	1.9221 3	1.9252 2	1.9283 2	1.9314 3	3	62	93	12	15	18	21	24	27	8
0.41	1.9345 4	1.9376 6	1.9407 8	1.9439 0	1.9470 3	1.9501 7	1.9533 1	1.9564 6	1.9596 1	1.9627 7	3	63	94	12	15	18	22	25	28	2
0.42	1.9659 3	1.9690 9	1.9722 7	1.9754 4	1.9786 2	1.9818 1	1.9850 0	1.9882 0	1.9914 1	1.9946 1	3	64	96	12	15	19	22	25	28	7
0.43	1.9978 2	2.0010 4	2.0042 6	2.0074 9	2.0107 3	2.0139 7	2.0172 1	2.0204 6	2.0237 1	2.0269 7	3	65	97	13	16	19	22	25	29	2
0.44	2.0302 4	2.0335 1	2.0367 8	2.0400 6	2.0433 5	2.0466 4	2.0499 4	2.0532 5	2.0565 6	2.0598 3	3	66	99	13	16	19	23	26	29	6
0.45	2.0631 8	2.0665 0	2.0698 3	2.0731 6	2.0765 0	2.0798 5	2.0832 5	2.0865 1	2.0899 8	2.0932 3	3	67	101	13	16	20	23	26	30	1
0.46	2.0966 5	2.1000 3	2.1034 1	2.1068 0	2.1101 9	2.1135 9	2.1170 0	2.1204 1	2.1238 2	2.1272 4	3	68	102	13	17	20	23	27	30	6
0.47	2.1306 7	2.1341 0	2.1375 4	2.1409 8	2.1444 3	2.1478 8	2.1513 4	2.1548 1	2.1582 8	2.1617 6	3	69	103	13	17	20	24	27	31	1
0.48	2.1652 4	2.1687 3	2.1722 2	2.1757 2	2.1792 2	2.1827 3	2.1862 5	2.1897 7	2.1933 0	2.1968 3	3	70	104	14	17	21	24	28	31	6
0.49	2.2003 7	2.2039 1	2.2074 6	2.2110 2	2.2145 8	2.2181 5	2.2217 2	2.2253 0	2.2288 8	2.2324 7	3	71	105	14	17	21	25	28	32	1
0.50	2.2360 7	2.2396 7	2.2432 1	2.2468 9	2.2505 3	2.2541 7	2.2577 3	2.2614 0	2.2650 4	2.2686 9	3	72	106	14	18	21	25	29	32	6
0.51	2.2723 5	2.2760 1	2.2796 5	2.2833 2	2.2870 1	2.2907 0	2.2944 9	2.2980 9	2.3017 9	2.3055 0	3	73	107	14	18	22	25	29	33	3
0.52	2.3092 2	2.3129 3	2.3166 6	2.3203 9	2.3241 3	2.3278 7	2.3316 8	2.3353 4	2.3391 1	2.3429 1	3	74	108	14	18	22	26	30	33	7
0.53	2.3466 8	2.3504 6	2.3542 5	2.3580 4	2.3618 4	2.3656 5	2.3694 5	2.3732 7	2.3770 9	2.3809 2	3	75	109	14	19	22	26	30	34	3
0.54	2.3847 6	2.3886 0	2.3924 4	2.3963 0	2.4001 6	2.4040 2	2.4079 7	2.4117 6	2.4156 5	2.4195 9	3	76	110	14	19	23	27	30	34	8
0.55	2.4234 5	2.4273 5	2.4312 6	2.4351 8	2.4391 0	2.4430 3	2.4469 6	2.4509 0	2.4548 5	2.4588 1	3	77	111	14	19	23	27	31	35	4
0.56	2.4627 7	2.4667 3	2.4707 7	2.4746 9	2.4786 7	2.4826 6	2.4866 6	2.4906 7	2.4946 0	2.4987 0	4	78	112	14	20	24	28	32	36	0
0.57	2.5027 2	2.5067 5	2.5107 9	2.5148 4	2.5188 9	2.5229 4	2.5270 1	2.5310 8	2.5351 6	2.5392 4	4	79	113	14	20	24	28	32	36	5
0.58	2.5433 3	2.5474 3	2.5515 3	2.5556 4	2.5597 6	2.5638 8	2.5680 1	2.5721 4	2.5762 9	2.5804 4	4	80	114	14	20	24	28	33	37	1
0.59	2.5845 9	2.5887 6	2.5929 3	2.5971 0	2.6012 9	2.6054 8	2.6096 7	2.6138 8	2.6180 9	2.6223 0	4	81	115	14	21	25	29	33	37	7
0.60	2.6265 3	2.6307 6	2.6350 0	2.6392 4	2.6434 9	2.6477 5	2.6520 1	2.6562 9	2.6605 6	2.6648 5	4	82	116	14	21	25	29	34	38	3
0.61	2.6691 4	2.6734 4	2.6777 5	2.6820 6	2.6863 8	2.6907 1	2.6950 4	2.6993 8	2.7037 3	2.7080 9	4	83	117	14	21	26	30	34	39	0
0.62	2.7124 2	2.7168 2	2.7211 9	2.7255 8	2.7299 7	2.7343 6	2.7387 7	2.7431 8	2.7476 2	2.7520 4	4	84	118	14	22	26	30	35	39	6
0.63	2.7564 0	2.7609 6	2.7653 4	2.7698 0	2.7742 6	2.7787 3	2.7832 0	2.7876 9	2.7921 8	2.7966 7	4	85	119	14	22	26	31	35	40	2
0.64	2.8011 8	2.8056 9	2.8102 1	2.8147 4	2.8192 7	2.8238 1	2.8283 6	2.8329 2	2.8374 8	2.8420 5	4	86	120	14	22	27	31	36	40	9
0.65	2.8466 3	2.8512 1	2.8558 0	2.8604 0	2.8650 1	2.8696 3	2.8742 5	2.8788 8	2.8835 2	2.8881 6	4	87	121	14	23	27	32	36	41	6
0.66	2.8928 1	2.8974 7	2.9021 4	2.9068 1	2.9115 0	2.9161 8	2.9208 8	2.9255 9	2.9303 2	2.9350 2	4	88	122	14	23	28	32	37	42	2
0.67	2.9397 5	2.9444 8	2.9492 2	2.9539 7	2.9587 3	2.9635 0	2.9682 7	2.9730 5	2.9778 4	2.9826 4	4	89	123	14	23	28	33	38	42	9
0.68	2.9874 4	2.9922 5	2.9970 7	3.0019 0	3.0067 4	3.0115 8	3.0164 3	3.0212 9	3.0261 6	3.0310 3	4	90	124	14	24	29	33	38	43	6
0.69	3.0359 1	3.0408 0	3.0457 1	3.0506 1	3.0555 2	3.0604 4	3.0653 7	3.0703 1	3.0752 5	3.0802 1	4	91	125	14	24	29	34	39	44	3
0.70	3.0851 7	3.0901 4	3.0951 2	3.1001 0	3.1051 0	3.1101 1	3.1151 1	3.1201 2	3.1251 5	3.1301 8	5	92	126	14	25	30	35	40	45	0
0.71	3.1352 3	3.1402 7	3.1453 3	3.1504 0	3.1554 7	3.1605 6	3.1656 5	3.1707 5	3.1758 7	3.1809 7	5	93	127	14	25	30	35	40	45	8
0.72	3.1860 9	3.1912 2	3.1963 6	3.2015 1	3.2066 7	3.2118 4	3.2170 1	3.2221 9	3.2273 8	3.2325 8	5	94	128	14	25	31	36	41	46	5
0.73	3.2377 9	3.2430 0	3.2482 6	3.2534 6	3.2587 0	3.2639 5	3.2692 0	3.2744 7	3.2797 4	3.2850 3	5	95	129	14	25	31	36	42	47	3
0.74	3.2903 2	3.2956 3	3.3009 4	3.3062 2	3.3115 7	3.3169 0	3.3222 4	3.3276 0	3.3329 6	3.3383 2	5	96	130	14	26	32	37	42	48	0
0.75	3.3437 0	3.3490 9	3.3544 8	3.3598 9	3.3653 2	3.3707 5	3.3761 8	3.3815 3	3.3870 9	3.3924 9	5	97	131	14	26	32	38	43	48	8
0.76	3.3979 5	3.4034 2	3.4089 1	3.4144 0	3.4199 1	3.4254 2	3.4309 5	3.4364 8	3.4419 3	3.4475 8	5	98	132	14	27	33	38	44	49	6
0.77	3.4520 8	3.4576 4	3.4632 2	3.4687 9	3.4743 8	3.4800 8	3.4856 9	3.4912 0	3.4968 3	3.5024 6	5	99	133	14	27	33	39	44	50	4
0.78	3.5091 1	3.5147 6	3.5204 9	3.5260 7	3.5317 9	3.5374 6	3.5431 6	3.5488 8	3.5545 1	3.5603 8	5	100	134	14	28	34	39	45	51	2
0.79	3.5660 4	3.5717 8	3.5775 4	3.5833 0	3.5890 7	3.5948 5	3.6006 4	3.6064 4	3.6122 7	3.6180 7	5	101	135	14	28	34	40	46	52	1

0.80	3.6239 0	3.6297 4	3.6355 8	3.6414 4	3.6473 0	3.6531 8	3.6590 6	3.6649 6	3.6708 6	3.6767 7		5 9	11 8	17 6	23 5	29 4	35 3	41 1	47 0	52 9
0.81	3.6827 0	3.6886 3	3.6945 7	3.7005 2	3.7064 8	3.7124 5	3.7184 3	3.7244 2	3.7304 2	3.7364 3		6 0	11 9	17 9	23 9	29 9	35 8	41 8	47 8	53 8
0.82	3.7424 5	3.7484 7	3.7545 1	3.7605 6	3.7666 2	3.7726 8	3.7787 6	3.7848 5	3.7909 5	3.7970 5		6 1	12 1	18 2	24 3	30 3	36 4	42 5	48 6	54 6
0.83	3.8031 6	3.8092 9	3.8154 3	3.8215 7	3.8277 3	3.8338 9	3.8400 7	3.8462 5	3.8524 5	3.8586 5		6 2	12 3	18 5	24 7	30 8	37 0	43 2	49 4	55 5
0.84	3.8648 7	3.8710 9	3.8773 3	3.8835 8	3.8898 3	3.8961 0	3.9023 7	3.9086 6	3.9149 5	3.9212 6		6 3	12 5	18 8	25 1	31 3	37 6	43 9	50 2	56 4
0.85	3.9275 8	3.9339 0	3.9402 4	3.9465 8	3.9529 4	3.9593 1	3.9656 9	3.9720 7	3.9784 7	3.9848 8		6 4	12 7	19 1	25 5	31 8	38 2	44 6	51 0	57 3
0.86	3.9913 0	3.9977 3	4.0041 7	4.0106 2	4.0170 8	4.0235 5	4.0300 3	4.0365 2	4.0430 2	4.0495 3		6 5	12 9	19 4	25 9	32 4	38 8	45 3	51 8	58 3
0.87	4.0560 6	4.0625 9	4.0691 3	4.0756 9	4.0822 5	4.0888 3	4.0954 1	4.1020 1	4.1086 2	4.1152 3		6 6	13 2	19 7	26 3	32 9	39 5	46 1	52 6	59 2
0.88	4.1218 6	4.1285 0	4.1351 5	4.1418 1	4.1484 9	4.1551 7	4.1618 6	4.1685 6	4.1752 8	4.1820 0		6 7	13 4	20 1	26 7	33 4	40 1	46 8	53 5	60 2
0.89	4.1887 4	4.1954 9	4.2022 4	4.2090 1	4.2157 8	4.2225 8	4.2293 8	4.2362 0	4.2430 2	4.2498 5		6 8	13 6	20 4	27 2	34 0	40 8	47 6	54 4	61 2
0.90	4.2567 0	4.2635 6	4.2704 2	4.2773 0	4.2841 9	4.2910 9	4.2980 0	4.3049 3	4.3118 6	4.3188 1		6 9	13 8	20 7	27 6	34 5	41 4	48 3	55 2	62 2
0.91	4.3257 6	4.3327 3	4.3397 0	4.3467 0	4.3537 1	4.3607 4	4.3677 4	4.3747 7	4.3818 2	4.3888 8		7 0	14 0	21 1	28 1	35 4	42 1	49 1	56 1	63 2
0.92	4.3959 5	4.4030 3	4.4101 2	4.4172 2	4.4243 4	4.4314 6	4.4386 0	4.4457 5	4.4529 1	4.4600 8		7 1	14 3	21 4	28 5	35 8	42 9	49 0	57 4	64 2
0.93	4.4672 7	4.4744 6	4.4816 7	4.4888 9	4.4961 2	4.5033 6	4.5106 2	4.5178 8	4.5251 6	4.5324 5		7 2	14 5	21 7	29 0	36 5	43 8	50 7	58 0	65 2
0.94	4.5397 5	4.5470 6	4.5543 9	4.5617 2	4.5690 7	4.5764 3	4.5838 0	4.5911 8	4.5985 8	4.6059 9		7 4	14 7	22 1	29 4	36 8	44 2	51 5	58 9	66 3
0.95	4.6134 0	4.6208 4	4.6282 8	4.6357 3	4.6432 0	4.6506 8	4.6581 7	4.6656 7	4.6731 9	4.6807 2		7 5	15 0	22 4	29 9	37 4	44 9	52 4	59 9	67 4
0.96	4.6882 6	4.6958 1	4.7033 7	4.7109 5	4.7185 3	4.7261 3	4.7337 5	4.7413 7	4.7490 1	4.7566 6		7 6	15 2	22 8	30 4	38 0	45 6	53 2	60 8	68 5
0.97	4.7643 2	4.7719 9	4.7796 8	4.7873 8	4.7950 1	4.8028 5	4.8105 0	4.8183 6	4.8260 3	4.8338 3		7 7	15 4	23 2	30 9	38 6	46 4	54 1	61 8	69 6
0.98	4.8416 2	4.8494 2	4.8572 3	4.8650 5	4.8728 9	4.8807 4	4.8886 0	4.8964 7	4.9043 6	4.9122 6		8 7	15 6	23 4	31 3	39 4	47 3	55 1	62 0	70 7
0.99	4.9201 7	4.9281 0	4.9360 4	4.9439 9	4.9519 5	4.9599 3	4.9679 1	4.9759 2	4.9839 3	4.9919 6		8 0	16 0	23 9	31 9	39 9	47 9	55 9	63 9	71 8

Table 8: Conversion of 5^y to 10^n in Five Figures

$5^y \rightarrow 10^n$

5^y	10^n	5^y	10^n	5^y	10^n	5^y	10^n	5^y	10^n
y=1	n=0.69897	y=21	n=14.67837	y=41	n=28.65777	y=61	n=42.63717	y=81	n=56.61657
2	1.39794	22	15.37734	42	29.35674	62	43.33614	82	57.31554
3	2.09691	23	16.07631	43	30.05571	63	44.03511	83	58.01451
4	2.79588	24	16.77528	44	30.75468	64	44.73408	84	58.71348
5	3.49485	25	17.47425	45	31.45365	65	45.43305	85	59.41245
6	4.19382	26	18.17322	46	32.15262	66	46.13202	86	60.11142
7	4.89279	27	18.87219	47	32.85159	67	46.83099	87	60.81039
8	5.59176	28	19.57116	48	33.55056	68	47.52996	88	61.50936
9	6.29073	29	20.27013	49	34.24953	69	48.22893	89	62.20833
10	6.98970	30	20.96910	50	34.94850	70	48.92790	90	62.90730
11	7.68867	31	21.66807	51	35.64747	71	49.62687	91	63.60627
12	8.38764	32	22.36704	52	36.34644	72	50.32584	92	64.30524
13	9.08661	33	23.06601	53	37.04541	73	51.02481	93	65.00421
14	9.78558	34	23.76498	54	37.74438	74	51.72378	94	65.70318
15	10.48455	35	24.46395	55	38.44335	75	52.42275	95	66.40215
16	11.18352	36	25.16292	56	39.14232	76	53.12172	96	67.10112
17	11.88249	37	25.86189	57	39.84129	77	53.82069	97	67.80009
18	12.58146	38	26.56086	58	40.54026	78	54.51966	98	68.49906
19	13.28043	39	27.25983	59	41.23923	79	55.21863	99	69.19803
20	13.97940	40	27.95880	60	41.93820	80	55.91760		

References

Osanyinpeju, K.L.: Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11)

Tables. 1st International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES), Osun State University, Theme: Advancing Technology and Environment Burdens (Challenges and Sustainable Solution) 5th- 7th November 2019 pp 957 – 968 (2019)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5794620>

Osanyinpeju, K.L.;Aderinlewo, A.A.;Dairo, O.U.;Adetunji, O.R.; Ajesegiri, E.S.A.: Development, Conversion

and Application of Osanyinpeju (Power of Base 2) and Antiosanyinpeju (Antipower of Base 2) with Lekan (Power of Base 5) and Antilekan (Antipower of Base 5) Tables.Ist International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Science, Osun State University. November 5 – 7, 2019 Pp 969 – 982 (2019).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5818003>

Osanyinpeju, K.L.: Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11), Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) and

Other Tables.Eliva Press SRL Publisher, MD-2060, bd. Cuza-Voda, ¼, of. 21 Chisinau, Republica Moldova, Europe 136 pp, (2020).

<https://www.amazon.com/Development-Kifilideen-Antikifilideen-Antipower-Tables/dp/B0884BP9TS>